

STUDY OF THE INCORPORATION OF ALLOYING ELEMENTS ON THE INTERFACE OF COPPER MATRIX NANOCOMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

Carbon nanofibres are promising reinforcements for metal matrix composites. A problem not yet solved is the promotion of a suitable copper/carbon interface. Several strategies have been envisaged for the incorporation of alloying elements (Ni, Co, B and Ti) at the interface. The effect on the microstructure, thermophysical and electrical properties is discussed.

Keywords: Metal matrix composites, Vapour grown carbon nanofibres, Interface, Electroless Plating, Hot-pressing.

INTRODUCTION

Vapour Grown Carbon Nanofibres (VGCNFs) exhibit excellent mechanical and thermophysical properties. Therefore they are very promising reinforcing materials for metal matrix composites (MMCs) in multiple applications [1]. The continuous manufacturing process of VGCNFs enables an immediate availability and excellent performance-to-cost ratio for the mass production of industrial components [2], over other candidates such as carbon fibers or nanotubes (CNTs). However, the manufacture of such a kind of material is not trivial, especially at high volume fraction of VGCNFs. Three key issues must be fulfilled in order to obtain high quality MMCs: dispersion of the reinforcement, high densification degree and promotion of a suitable matrix/reinforcement interface. Regarding interface there is a lack of interaction between copper and carbon [3]. This is a problem that is urgent to solve in order to get advantage of the performance of VGCNFs in MMCs, especially for thermal management applications where low coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) and high thermal conductivity are required.

EXPERIMENTAL

Composites Manufacture

The carbon nanofibres used in the present study were purchased from Showa Denko KK (VGCF grade). The amount of nanofibres in the final composites was 20 vol. %. There is a poor wetting between the copper and carbon [3]. Therefore it is necessary to improve this interface in order to achieve composites with the required properties. One interesting solution is the addition of elements able to interact at interfacial level. In this

sense different methods, derived from the electroless plating technique, have been envisaged for the incorporation of elements (Ni, Co, B and Ti) at the copper/carbon interface. The first method consists of duplex coatings through the electroless plating methods. In this method a thin layer of nickel [4] or cobalt [5] has been coated on the surface of the nanofibres, followed by a second layer of copper [6], which will be the matrix after the consolidation. The second method consisted of the coating of the nanofibres by an electroless copper alloy, in this case copper plus a small quantity of boron [7]. The last third method is based on the mixture of copper coated nanofibres with metallic nanopowders, in this case, Ti nanoparticles (Argonide Corp, USA). Two different amounts of Ti (0.3 and 5 wt %) were studied. Once the composite powders are obtained they are consolidated by hot-pressing at 900 °C and 35 MPa.

Characterisation

Chemical, microstructural and thermophysical characterisation has been carried-out on composite powders and consolidated composites. The chemical characterisation was performed by the EDS (Energy Dispersive Spectrometry) microprobe attached to the Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) in order to assess possible contamination during the coating process and oxygen amount and determine the quantity of interfacial elements. Furthermore a more accurate value for these elements was given by the ICP-OES (Inductively coupled plasma - Optical Emission Spectrometer) technique. The extent of densification was calculated by comparing the real density with the theoretical one. The microstructure of the consolidated composites was inspected by optical and scanning electron microscopy. The samples were cut and embedded into epoxy resin holders. Once cured, the samples were progressively polished using a silicon carbide grid, and finally polished with diamond paste to a mirror finish. These samples were etched with a FeCl₃:HCl:H₂O (1:1:1) solution for 7 seconds. The presence of an interfacial layer and the distribution of the alloying element was observed by TEM (Transmission electron microscopy) and a Dual Beam FIB (Focuses Ion Beam), where the FIB mills away material whilst the image is acquired using an SEM. The coefficient of thermal expansion was CTE was measured by dilatometry while the thermal conductivity was calculated by the indirect method through the expression (1).

$$\lambda(T) = a(T) \cdot c_p(T) \cdot \rho(T) \quad (1)$$

In which λ is the thermal conductivity (W/mK), a is the thermal diffusivity (m²/s), C_p is the specific heat (J/kgK) and ρ is the density (kg/m³). The thermal diffusivity was calculated through the laser flash technique, while the specific heat was calculated through Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC). The density was measured by the Archimedes method under absolute ethanol.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Microstructure

The inspection and the microstructure of the pristine nanofibres were analyzed in a previous work [6]. It was concluded there that these type of nanofibres present a more graphitic structure over from the ones form other manufacturers. Moreover the nanofibres were clean from the metallic seeds employed for their synthesis. The copper coating description and characterization is also reported there. Figure 1 shows the microstructure of the composites modified with Ni. The nickel coating is successfully deposited on the surface of the nanofibres forming a continuous coverage (see Figure 1a).

Figure 1 – Microstructures of the Cu/Ni/VGCNFs composites: a) Nickel plating, b) Duplex coating after copper deposition, c) Consolidated composite and d) EDS Ni mapping.

The copper coating on the nickel coated VGCNFs is shown on Figure 1b. The copper coating on the nanofibres was seen to be granular and homogeneous. As shown in Figure 2c the consolidated composite shows a fine distribution of the nanofibres in the matrix with a low presence of nanofibre agglomerates. The distribution of the composite elements was checked by EDS mapping (see Figure 1d for Ni). This confirmed the good distribution of the carbon nanofibres within the copper matrix. The amount of nickel was determined in 7 wt % (ICP-OES). In addition, the amount of oxygen was shown to be very low (> 0.1 wt %). The TEM inspection revealed that a low amount of nickel was present in the proximity of the interface, but the amount of nickel in the copper matrix was high. This measurement suggested that the amount of nickel, formerly present on the interface, diffused into the copper while the consolidation was carried out.

Figure 2 shows the microstructure of the Cu/VGCNFs modified with Cobalt, following a similar procedure as for the Cu/Ni/VGCNFs composites. The microstructure of the cobalt coated nanofibres is shown in Figure 2a.

Figure 2 – Microstructures of the Cu/Co/VGCNFs composites: a) Cobalt plating and b) Consolidated composite.

Cobalt deposits were found not only on the nanofibres, but also as tiny particle precipitates between the nanofibres. The microstructure of the consolidated composite is shown Figure 2b. After the consolidation the nanofibres were well distributed in the matrix, although some small agglomerates (>5 μm) are present. The final amount of cobalt was around 9 wt %. The distribution of the different constituents of the composite was inspected by SEM inspection and EDS mapping, showing that interfacial element (cobalt) was present in terms of isolated deposits. This suggested that the interfacial element was not located on the copper/carbon interface. The presence of oxygen in the composite was quite low.

The microstructure of the composites containing Boron is shown in Figure 3. The incorporation of Boron was carried-out during the deposition of copper, coming as impurity from the reducing agent employed in the electroless plating process (from the Sodium Borohydride). The Boron content in the samples was very low (0.001 wt % by ICP-OES). The microstructure was inspected by SEM and TEM. Firstly the coating resulted to be smooth and homogeneous with small amounts of VGCNFs bundles. Each image was selected to be representative of the bulk microstructure. From the inspection by SEM an excellent distribution of the nanofibres and a homogeneous microstructure were observed. Moreover, the detailed observation by TEM (Figure 3b), shows that the carbon-copper interface is continuous, leading to a good physical contact between these two phases.

Figure 4 shows the composites samples after the Ti nanoparticles addition. The mixture with copper coated nanofibres was intensively inspected by SEM. As shown in Figure 4a no evidence of the presence of Ti particle agglomeration was seen during the SEM inspection even at 5 w % of Ti.

Figure 3 – Microstructures of the Cu/B/VGCNFs composites: a) Cu-B electroless plating and b) TEM images of the Cu/C interface.

This suggested that the nanoparticles were finely distributed through the coated nanoparticles. The consolidated samples are shown in Figure 4b and c for the 0.3 and 5 w % of Ti (optical images, in order to give a representative macroscopic view). The microstructure of the sample with 0.3 wt % of Ti resulted to be more homogeneous as compared with the one containing 5 wt %. In this case the lower amount of Ti prevents the formation of agglomerates. The mechanism of the formation of these agglomerates is still unknown and more work is required to elucidate this effect. The presence of TiC was detected by XRD and EFTEM mapping [7]. As shown in Figure 4d, in the case of the composite with 5 wt % of Ti an interfacial layer of TiC of about 100nm is formed after the diffusion of Ti through the copper. The TEM inspection has not shown evidences of the presence of TiC at the interface of the 0.3 wt % Ti composite.

Figure 4 – Microstructures of the Cu/Ti/VGCNFs composites: a) Coated VGCNFs + Ti nanopowders (5 wt %), b) Consolidated sample (0.3 w % Ti), c) Consolidated sample (5 w % Ti) d) EFTM Ti mapping.

Thermophysical properties

The thermophysical properties are shown in Table 1. The material with Co content was discarded to be measured due to the inhomogeneous microstructure. The values of the densification are also shown. In all the cases is above 5 %, although the composite with 5 w % of Ti has the lowest value. This should be connected with the high presence of agglomerates (see Figure 4) in the composites with higher amount of Ti. Extra Ti would also alloy with the Cu and reduce the thermal conductivity of the matrix. The properties of pure copper and a Cu/VGCNFs plain material with no additives [8] are shown as a comparison of properties.

Regarding the CTE, only slight reduction as compared with copper is achieved (see the last column of Table 1). The composite with nickel expands even more than the copper. Moreover the composites containing Boron and the Ti are more effective over those including Nickel. The composite with the less amount of Ti shows the lowest value of CTE. This can be attributed to the formation of carbides that allows the transmission of stresses through the interface.

Table 1 – Microstructures of the Cu/Ti/VGCNFs composites.

Sample Ref.	Thermal Diffusivity (cm ² /s)	Specific Heat (J/KgK)	Density (g/cm ³)	Densification (%)	Thermal conductivity (W/mK)	CTE (room T ^e)
Pure Copper	1.12	384	8.93	100	395	16.5
Cu/CNFs	0.74	503	7.51	99.67	280	16.4
Cu/Ni/CNFs	0.17	505	7.47	98.30	64	17
Cu/B/CNFs	0.78	514	7.56	98.51	306	15.6
Cu/0.3Ti/CNFs	0.80	517	7.52	99.16	311	13.6
Cu/5Ti/CNFs	0.56	493	7.27	97.47	200	15.7

Concerning the thermal conductivity a similar trend as for the CTE was observed, On the one hand the composite containing Nickel shows the lower value of thermal diffusivity and conductivity. This can be explained through the observed microstructure. The Nickel instead of being placed at the interface it was solubilised through the copper matrix. This is detrimental for the thermal conductivity of the matrix. On the other hand the composites containing B and Ti show better results. This would be attributed to the formation of carbides, which are beneficial for the thermal transport at the metal/carbon interface [9]. In any case the values of the thermal conductivity are lower than the pure copper. There are two main possibilities to explain these low values of thermal conductivity:

- (1) The thermal conductivity of the carbon nanofibres was estimated theoretically to be 1200 W/mK [10]. If the real value is much lower than this given by the manufacturer this would explain the low values of thermal diffusivity and conductivity shown by the copper composites.
- (2) Poor metal/copper interface. The thermal transport in metals (like copper) is based on electrons, while the thermal transport of nanofibres is based on phonon. Therefore scattering at the interface will take place.

As shown in Table 1 the diffusivity is the factor than in accordance with the expression (1) mainly dominates the final value of the thermal conductivity therefore the efforts should be addressed to the increase of the thermal diffusivity especially through the interface The results thermal diffusivity on Table 1 shown an improvement of the composites containing B and Ti (0.3 w %) over the plain composite (no interface), but this enhancement is not enough. Further efforts must be addressed to the optimization of the Ti and B amount of the composites or the inclusion of alternative elements at the interface able to react with carbon to promote the formation of carbides such as Mo, Ta, Cr or W.

CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER WORKS

The present study contains a preliminary work for the modification the interface of copper/carbon nanofibre composites with alloying elements such as Nickel, Cobalt, Boron and Ti. Different approaches have been used for the incorporation of these elements: duplex electroless coatings (Ni + Cu), coating of copper alloys (Cu+B) and the addition of metal nanoparticles (Ti). Once the composite powders were obtained they were consolidated by hot-pressing. The best result in term of microstructure and themophysical properties are achieved by the incorporation of B and Ti due to the formation of interfacial carbides. In this case the use of high amount of Ti (5 w %) is detrimental due to the presence of big nanofibres agglomerates. There is a reduction in the CTE but regarding the thermal conductivity it was not possible to obtain a value higher than the value of copper. There are two main explanations: low thermal conductivity of the carbon nanofibres (< 1200 W/mK) and weak interface. Therefore further efforts should be addressed to the optimization of the content of B and Ti and the incorporation of alternative element able to react with carbon to promote the formation of interfacial carbides, such as Mo, Ta, Cr or W.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This study was complementary funded by the European Commission grant project "New Materials for Extreme Environments - ExtreMat", contract ref. NMP3-CT-2004-500253", by ESA/ESTEC grant of project "Power and thermal management of wide bandgap semiconductors" Ref: 17441/03/NL/CH" and by the Spanish ministry of science and education (MEC) through the grant proyect: "Nuevos materiales para encapsulado de dispositivos de SiC de muy alta potencia, temperatura y frecuencia", ref. TEC2005-07937-C02-02/MIC. The help of Dr. Neubauer (Austrian research centres) in the measurement of the thermal expansion and conductivity is also appreciated.

References

1. S. Arai, M. Endo, S. Hashizume, and Y. Shimojima, *Electrochemical Communications* 6, 1029 (2004).
2. I. Kang, Y.Y. Heung, J.H. Kim, J.W. Lee, R. Gollapudi, S. Subramaniam, et al, *Composites: Part B* 37 (2006) 382-394.
3. D.A. Mortimer, and M. Nicholas, *J. Mater Sci*, 5, 149 (1970).
4. F. Wang, S. Arai, M. Endo, *Electrochemistry Communications* 6 (2004) 1042-1044.
5. X. Chen, J. Xia, J. Peng, W. Li, S. Xie, *Composites Science and technology* 60 (1999) 301-306.
6. J. Barcena, J. Maudes, J. Coletto, J.L. Baldonado, J.M. Gomez de Salazar, *Composites Science and technology* 68, 1384(2008).
7. J.C. Lloyd, J. Barcena and W.J. Clegg, *Cambridge CNT Symposium 2008*.
8. J. Barcena, R. Martinez, J. Maudes, M. Garcia de Cortazar, I. Caro y J. Coletto, *X Congreso Nacional de materiales (Donostia-San Sebastián, June 2008)*.
9. Th. Schubert, B. Trindade, T. Weißgarber, B. Kieback, *Materials Science and Engineering A* 475 (2008) 39-44.
10. Showa Denko www.sdk.co.jp. VGCF MSDS